

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF FORMING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTS OF NATURE

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the theoretical foundations and importance of forming primary school students with scientific concepts about nature.*

Key words: *Primary school students, scientific concepts of nature, natural science.*

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ НАУЧНЫХ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЙ О ПРИРОДЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена информация о теоретических основах и важности формирования у младших школьников научных представлений о природе.*

Ключевые слова: *Младшие школьники, научные представления о природе, естествознание.*

By teaching students science, the teacher not only equips them with the knowledge, training and skills necessary for continuing education and practical activities, but also forms their worldview, will, character, develops their intellectual abilities. Accordingly, he develops forms and methods of teaching natural science.

Properly organized communication with nature enriches and deepens the sense of beauty in young schoolchildren, they develop the ability to self-evaluate their own actions and work, and these qualities lead to the understanding of moral and ethical norms of behavior. , it is necessary to educate responsibility and duty towards others. In the process of communicating with nature, respect and affection for one's friends and elders emerges.

The methodology of teaching science has the following tasks:

- clarifying the importance and place of science as a subject in the system of general education and comprehensive education;
- selection and combination (synthesis) of natural science materials;
- to determine its educational and educational tasks.

Teaching natural science in primary school does not consist only of introducing some things in the life of nature - phenomena and plants, animals, and the external features of a person. Teaching natural science reveals the interactions between various objects of animate and inanimate

nature, between animate nature and human labor in a form that can be understood by young schoolchildren, fosters deep love for nature, protection of its wealth. and should cultivate the desire to use with caution.

The elementary school science course covers a wide range of natural phenomena, so it is sometimes difficult to make observations in relation to the studied phenomena. Therefore, when choosing objects for the initial study of natural science, the following should be taken into account: the age characteristics of the students, the comprehensibility of the studied material, its educational and developmental effect, the presence of local history material, the acquired knowledge it is necessary to take into account the possibility of using the living nature corner of the school and the work in the educational area.

The fulfillment of all educational and educational tasks depends on the correct choice of methods. It is impossible to develop observation in young students without independent observations in nature, it is impossible to understand the life of plants and animals without directly studying living organisms, without practical work on growing plants and caring for animals, agriculture It is impossible to form practical training and skills of hard work.

It is impossible to know the importance of any method used, whether the students have mastered the material, whether they have formed the necessary ideas and concepts, without determining the educational results. Only based on this information, any method can be correctly evaluated.

The development of the issue of teaching methods and the issue of training equipment are also closely related, because training equipment and other equipment are the basis for the formation of scientific ideas and concepts. The methodology of natural science also looks at the material assessment of teaching - natural science room, corner of living nature, educational and experimental area, geography field, organization and use of technical means of teaching. ri will not be able to be carried.

Konstantin Dmitrievich Ushinsky (1824-1870) was one of the representatives of advanced pedagogical ideas in the middle of the 19th century. He singled out the method of observation as the most effective method for learning about nature. Ushinsky suggested to start introducing children to nature by studying their own place, their own country, in which the impressions obtained from reading a book or the teacher's information can be verified by the child's observations. Ushinsky noted that one of the main methods of studying the nature of one's place is observation, because they help to create observability. In the book "Children's World", Ushinsky

showed how observation of nature is necessary in order to teach children the simple logical tasks underlying the development of speech.

Alexander Yakovlevich Gerd (1841-1888) was the first to propose the system of teaching nature with observations, experiments and excursions. He emphasized that visual teaching should be in accordance with the specific state of the child's perception. Gerd created such a system, in which the study of nature begins with inanimate nature, he developed a methodology for teaching the course of inanimate nature in elementary grades. It is a textbook called "Short Course in Nature", as well as "Earth, Air, Water" he wrote a teaching manual and a methodical manual on teaching them entitled "Subject Lessons in Elementary School" (1883). For a long time, this book has been the main guide for the still life course.

In his research, M.N.Skatkin paid great attention to the methods of organizing extracurricular activities in natural science and the issues of activating children's cognitive activities in nature studies.

In connection with the main directions of the reform of general education and vocational schools, the issues of teaching natural science have been resolved in a new way. The study of the course is conducted in two directions. The first involves introducing children to people's social life and work, educating them about the culture of behavior. In the second, it is necessary to introduce nature in direct communication with it, to form ideas about natural objects and phenomena, to treat nature with responsibility, to educate the culture of behavior in nature, and to organize valuable activities in nature protection. will be done. Acquaintance with nature is carried out on the basis of observations on excursions, educational trips, and practical work.

The subject "Introduction to the environment" is closely related to other subjects of the primary school. Observing the life of nature and society, people's work helps to better understand the teaching material of subjects such as mother tongue and Russian language, labor education, visual activity, mathematics. In these lessons, during the classes on introducing the world to the environment, the students' ideas about nature will be expanded, enriched, and will have a great practical direction.

"Natural Science" is a continuation of the "Environment Introduction" course and includes various fields of natural sciences. Studying natural sciences in grades 3-4 implies the consistent development of ideas and concepts that inanimate nature and living nature form a whole, and therefore they are interdependent.

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